

The Jordanian Strategy to Contain the Impacts of the Syrian Refugee Crisis

SUPERVISOR: DR. SHAHID TASLEEM

MOHAMMED B. E. SAAIDA

MMAJ ACADEMY OF INTERNATIONAL STUDIES

JAMIA MILLIA ISLAMIA, NEW DELHI, 110025

Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to clarify the Jordanian strategy to contain the impacts of the Syrian refugee crisis on Jordan. The study starts with a review of the historical background of the influx of Syrian refugees to Jordan since 2011 till 2017, then followed by a literature review of some studies that have dealt with Syrian refugees' crisis. The study discussed the impacts of the influx of Syrian refugees on Jordan's economy, education, healthcare, shelter and water and security threats. The researcher addresses the main elements of the Jordanian strategies aiming at containing the negative impacts of the Syrian refugees. This study argued that despite that the Jordanian government had built up the Jordan Response Plans for the Syria refugees' crisis and the vulnerable affected hosting communities (JRPSC) empowered by 12 teams to work through special governmental institution and supported by international community organization to implement it, still the Syrian refugees are forming growing burdens on Jordan especially the vulnerable hosting communities. The Jordan government followed the strategies depending on the Jordanian humanitarian response through JRPSC and in synchrony with the international community.

Key words: Jordanian strategy; impacts; Syrian refugees; response;

الاستراتيجية الأردنية لاحتواء آثار أزمة اللاجئين السوريين

ملخص:

هدفت هذه الدراسة إلى توضيح الاستراتيجية الأردنية لاحتواء آثار أزمة اللاجئين السوريين على الأردن، بدأت هذه الدراسة بمراجعة سريعة لتاريخ اللجوء السوري إلى الأردن منذ العام 2011 وحتى 2017، ثم تليت باستعراض لدراسات سابقة تناولت موضوع الدراسة، لقد ركز الباحث في دراسة على جوانب محددة من آثار اللاجئين السوريين على الأردن وهي الاقتصاد والتعليم والصحة والإسكان والماء والأخطار الأمنية.

لقد تناولت الدراسة أهم عناصر الاستراتيجية الأردنية لاحتواء الآثار السلبية لأزمة اللجوء السوري في الأردن، لقد وجدت الدراسة بأنه وعلى الرغم من قيام الأردن بإنشاء خطط الاستجابة الأردنية للأزمة السورية والتي تم تدعيمها باتي عشر فريقاً يعملون من خلال مؤسسات حكومية وبمساعدة المنظمات الدولية المختصة، إلا أن الأردن لا يزال يرحح تحت الأعباء المتزايدة للأزمة السورية وخصوصاً المناطق الحضرية التي يسكنها اللاجئون، كما اتبعت الحكومة الأردنية استراتيجية بالاعتماد على الدعم الإنساني من خلال خطة الاستجابة الأردنية لأزمة اللاجئين السوريين والمجتمعات الأردنية المتضررة والتي تتناغم مع المجتمع الدولي.

كلمات مفتاحية: الاستراتيجية الأردنية، آثار، لاجئين سوريين، استجابة.

Introduction:

Jordan is one of the main countries that had been affected directly by the consequences of the Syrian Crisis which started in 2011 till now in 2017. In the past, Jordan was sharply hit by the Palestinian (1947, 1967) and the Iraqi (2003) crises. In reaction, the Jordanian foreign policies and strategies were guided by the high interests of the Jordanian state. The formal positions reflected the Jordanian attitudes and policies towards each issue locally, regionally and internationally.

Jordan started to receive Syrian refugees by the beginning of the Syrian crisis. The number reached over 600 thousand refugees seeking asylum (Abisaab et al., 2014). The major impacts for Jordan will be discussed fully in the study only on the economy, education, healthcare, shelter, water, and security. The security fears that occurred with the rise of terrorism as a consequence of the Syrian crisis will be put into the debate, too.

Jordan's stance on Syria's predicament ultimately bases itself on political, security, social and economic considerations. Jordan has attempted to balance regional and international influences so as to distance itself from any direct involvement in Syria, in favor of any side; thus, the only Jordanian positions that were explicitly critical of the regime came under the cover of the Arab League resolutions (Satic, 2014).

The need for improving the Jordanian strategy in order to contain the Syrian refugee crisis remains open, regardless of whether the Syrian regime falls or not. However, the deepening of the crisis, the continuation of the conflict, and Jordan's geographic location make it harder for the Kingdom to deal with the Syrian refugee crisis, which is one of the main components of the Syrian question in the future. Nevertheless, since Jordan had previously experienced the waves of refugees, it has become easier for the Jordanian government to deal with the current crises.

Statement of the Problem:

The study of the Jordanian strategy to contain the impacts of the Syrian refugees is an attempt to understand how the Jordanian strategy is dealing with the Syrian refugees in vulnerable hosting communities in Jordan. This attempt cannot be accomplished without exploring the varying effects that are ruling the Jordanian policy and plans. There are major factors playing major roles in the decision making of Jordanian strategy to contain the impacts of the Syrian refugees:

1. The Syrian refugee consequences: Jordan has received over 600 thousand refugees seeking asylum pushed by the violence in Syria. Jordan is a country with a shortage of resources. The refugee crisis had created bad impacts on the Jordanian economy, social and security dimensions. At the same time, empowering the Jordanian market with skillful and cheap labor power is one of the good impacts of the Syrian refugee presence in Jordan. Jordan, having short economic resources, is trying to host the refugees and simultaneously assist the affected Jordanian people. Five camps for refugees were opened with the help of the United Nations: Za'atari, Azraq, Marjeeb Al Fhood, Rukban and Hadallat refugee camps, while other Syrians also spread in various urban areas in Jordan.
2. The consequences of the Syrian refugee crisis are faced by strategy built by the Jordanian government. The main elements of the strategy are premised upon several factors such as the humanitarian basic aid, the political stance, the positive and negative consequences, and the International fund helping Jordan to face the problem. In addition to that, the Jordanian government took actions to face the crisis by building The Jordanian Response through (JRPSC), in order to be in harmony with the efforts done by the International Community.

Research Objectives:

1. To elucidate the consequences of the influx of Syrian refugees into Jordan.
2. To clarify the Jordanian strategy to contain these consequences on Jordan for the benefit of the Syrian refugees and the affected Jordanian hosting communities.

Research Questions:

The questions of the study are:

1. What are the consequences of the influx of Syrian refugees into Jordan?
2. What are the response plans in the Jordanian strategy to contain the negative impacts of Syrian refugee crisis for the Syrian refugees and in the affected Jordanian hosting communities?

Methodology:

In order to answer the research questions, an objective, analytical, and descriptive route will be adopted. The researcher will carry out through a literature review. An overall view of the Jordanian policy in dealing with the Syrian refugees would help to understand from the Jordanian strategy to contain the impacts of the Syrian refugee crisis.

The nature and scope of this research are qualitative, dealing mostly with accounts and appraisals of chronological historical events, incorporating original analysis, before offering conclusions. Analyzing the variables that caused the -supposed turn- in the Jordanian strategy vis-à-vis the Syrian refugees and the affected Jordanian hosting communities. The methodology is to ascertain what actual negative consequences that led to formulate the Jordanian strategy to contain the impacts of the Syrian crisis by depending on the governmental and international organizations official reports regarding the Syrian existence in Jordan and their impacts on the Jordanian people life.

Historical Background:

By the end 2011 of the Syrian crisis, the Syrian refugees started to arrive in Jordan, the country was already been full of Iraqi refugees and worry of accepting more. The previous experiences with Palestinian and Iraqi refugees raised concerns over the existence of refugee populations and the negative implications of hosting more refugees in the middle of regional economic, political, and security challenges such as terrorism expansion form terroristic organizations through the Syrian refugees. These experiences reflected in the development of the country's policy towards the Syrian refugees.

The northern parts of Jordan hosted the first refugee wave fleeing of violence to control the political demonstrations in Syria. About 2,000 Syrians arrived in Jordan by the end of 2011, which was a small number to be dealt with by the Jordanian government and had no severe impact on the hosting communities. Many of them believed they would soon go back to their homeland (UNCHR Report, 2012). However, the following years witnessed greater floods of refugees into the Kingdom.

The UNHCR and the Jordanian government hastily opened Zaatari refugee camp over the course of two hot weeks in July 2012 because it became very clear that the influx would accelerate. The initial several hundred residents multiplied to 15,000 by August 2012 (Remnick, 2013). Now in the seventh year of the Syrian civil war, Zaatari refugee camp had grown into one of the most crowded concentrated population centers in the region, the fourth-largest "city" in Jordan, and the second-largest refugee camp in the world (Weston, 2015).

The impact of the Syria crisis in Jordan is multifaceted, spanning almost all sectors of the economy and affecting – with varying degrees of intensity – all geographic areas. On the macroeconomic side, the crisis continues to aggravate economic difficulties and exacerbate existing vulnerabilities, thereby casting a shadow over public finance performance. The crisis has

placed a significant burden on budgets and is overstressing services across all affected sectors.

While some sectors may have benefited from the population increase, the overall impact of the crisis on the economy has been detrimental. Although the influx of some 630,000 Syrian refugees — in addition to other 750,000 Syrians who were in Jordan before the crisis — is an important component of this impact, it represents only part of the picture. Another primary destabilizing economic factor has been the regional trade distortions caused by the crisis, which is directly linked to increasing levels of national debt and a worsening trade deficit.

The Jordanian government built up response strategies and plans to face the impacts made by the refugees. The main partners are the United Nations special agency The Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) and other international organizations. Jordan has proved the most highly sophisticated regional reaction to the Syrian refugee crisis of all the major neighboring host countries. Led by the Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation, Jordan demonstrated its willingness and readiness to use the Syrian population as a lever to garner international development aid through the Jordan Response Plan for the Syria Crisis (JRPSC). The plan is described as “the first nationally-led response of its kind, joining refugee and development responses in one complete national plan that targeting the Syrian refugees and the affected Jordanian, as well. (JRPSC, 2013).

Review of Literature:

Elisabeth Ådnegard in her Master thesis titled *Jordan: Surprisingly stable* (Ådnegard, 2014) presents an analysis of the stability in Jordan and its main objective is to explain this stability despite the massive influx of Syrian refugees. The researcher found that over the years, research has demonstrated that conflict spreads to the host country as a consequence of the massive influx of refugees.

The study concludes that mainly three factors have kept Jordan stable: the majority of the Jordanian people's wish for stability, or rather their fear of ending up in the same situation as their neighbors; the political and economic support from foreign actors and patrons; and finally, Jordan's willingness and capability to control the borders and provide security. This study shows that all three factors are intertwined as stability is being secured through monetary and military support, which helps Jordan pay the military and intelligence expenses needed to prevent spillover from Syria. This support also pays for the political support from the citizens through subsidies and public sector employment in an effort to shield the citizens from the de facto deteriorating economic situation. This fragile stability has been the situation in Jordan the past three years, 2011-2014, but there are no guarantees that this will continue.

The book *Protecting Syrian Refugees: Laws, Policies, and Global Responsibility*, by the Share of Elena Nouredine and others (Nouredine et al., 2015) came out the contribution of 43 institutions' staffs and officials of the following individuals, organizations and government ministries. It shows that the Syrian Civil war has caused approximately 2.7 million Syrians to leave their country since 2011, and double that many are expected to have fled Syria by the end of 2014. The Syrian refugee crisis has brought tremendous challenges to the region. Jordan is the fourth most water-stressed country in the world, with insufficient potable water for its own people. The authors are talking about the impact of Syrian refugees on the water resources in Jordan. Also, the book includes Lebanon and Egypt who have extremely volatile political environments and unstable governments.

Maha Kattaa analyzes in her paper *Social protection and employment for Syrian refugees in Jordan* (Kattaa, 2013) the legal framework of social protection and employment for refugees in general with a focus on Syrian refugees in Jordan and levels of implementation, as well as proposing policy directions on the national and regional levels. This paper focuses on the country's historical and legal contexts and then provides an overview

of the provision of social protection to Syrian refugees in Jordan and the challenges they are facing to gain access to the formal labor market and social protection mechanisms.

The Author Curtis R. Ryan in the article *Jordanian foreign policy and the Arab Spring* (Ryan, 2014) is dealing with the Jordanian foreign policy towards the Arab Spring. He talks about the Jordanian relations with the countries that have popular political movements. The Jordanian dilemma about Syria was certainly rooted deeply in the refugee crisis. But the regime was also worried about potential Islamist ascendancy in Damascus after the war, even suggesting that a Muslim Brotherhood axis, of new Islamist-led regimes, might be emerging in the region. The same regime that had earlier feared a Shia axis, including Lebanon, Syria, Iraq, and Iran was now visualizing a potential Sunni axis, but not one marked by Jordanian-style moderation. The Jordanians also feared rising Islamist militancy in Syria, and the return of Jordanian Salafi jihadists once the war was over.

The report *Impact of Syrian refugees on the Jordanian labour market* by Erik Stave and Solveig Hillesund (Hillesund, 2015) presents the main findings of a household survey conducted in the Jordanian governorates of Amman, Irbid, and Mafraq between February and March 2014. It aimed at assessing the implications of the large influx of Syrian Refugees onto the labor market in the three geographical areas. The results are based on information gathered on the current labor market situation, as well as some of the changes that have occurred since the beginning of the Syrian Refugee influx into Jordan in March 2011.

The report reached to conclusions; there is a loss of opportunity for increased employment of Jordanians in newly emerged low skilled jobs; increased unemployment and competition for existing jobs; future threats of crowding out in the labor market; an overall deterioration in working conditions leading to increased decent work deficits in Jordan.

Before we embark on discussing the available literature on Syrian refugees in Jordan, it is important to take the previous points into consideration. Not all of them would be necessarily very sufficient and enough in the case of Syrian refugees in Jordan, but at least the studies will help to extract our variables as explained below.

The consequences of the Syrian refugee Crisis on Jordan:

In this study, the researcher will give a brief overview of the main negative impacts of the Syrian refugee crisis on Jordan. The field of focus will be on the economy, education, healthcare, shelter, water, and security threats impacts.

1. Economy:

Jordan as a resource-poor country that depends on external support for economic stability, has a very vulnerable economy to external economic shocks. Just before the arrival of Syrian refugees, Jordan's economy was facing an important period of shrinkage, as the economy suffered from two such shocks. First, waves from the international financial crisis of 2008 shook the foundations of Jordan's economy, leading to a notable reduction in foreign direct investment and private capital flows to Jordan (Ahid & Augustine, 2012). Second, the Arab Spring caused a regional economic decline and weakened several of Jordan's key trading partners. For example, disturbances to the flow of natural gas from Egypt sparked unstable variations in the regional oil supply and prices. Deteriorating global commodity values, limited exports, and reduced transmittals negatively triggered Jordan's economy during this period. (Dooley, 2009). The precipitous drop had negative consequences for unemployment and rising product prices in Jordan.

As for the unemployment, many Jordanians blame the influx of Syrian refugees for increasing the levels of unemployment. The International Labor Organization reported unemployment among Jordanians grew from 14.5% in March 2011 to 22% by 2014 (Hillesund, 2015) Although Syrians

can't legally work in Jordan, ILO estimated that 160,000 Syrians are working in the informal job sector, mainly in construction, service, and agricultural jobs. According to the survey published by ILO, 96% of Jordanians believed Syrians were taking their jobs. Despite the Syrian presence, it is more likely the regional and international economic crisis, along with Jordan's preexisting structural economic issues, are responsible for the increase in unemployment (Hillesund, 2015)..

Reports propose the suppression of salaries in Jordan's informal economic sector represents the most touchable undesirable effect of the Syrian entry into the Jordanian workforce (Hillesund, 2015). Decreasing pressure on wages in the informal employment market threatens to make the economic situation of Jordanians who rely on them untenable. The 14% of Jordanians living below the poverty line rely on wages from informal employment for half of their earnings (Karasapan, 2015). Thus, suppressing wages not only increases labor exploitation and deteriorates work standards as job competition in the informal sector grows, but also encourages negative coping mechanisms like child labor and intensifies poverty among the most vulnerable Jordanian communities. The World Bank also contends that the downward pressure on wages may be causing a decrease in the Jordanian national labor force participation rate (World Bank, 2014).

The presence of the Syrians on the Jordanian economy, in particular, the informal sectors have increased marginalization in Jordan. Wages went down as the country's most vulnerable inhabitants tolerate the effect of the costs in the form of descending pressure on wages and rising unemployment rate, Jordanian market benefit from increased Syrian demand and a larger workforce. (Francis, 2015).

2. Education:

As public schools became overloaded with Syrian refugees, the Jordanians expressed worries about shortage class times, and double-shifting, overcrowded classrooms. Before to the arrival of the Syrian

refugees, there were advances in the education sector. The situation led to heightened community and government frustration over the new stress on public schools (Achilli, 2015).

The refugees under the age of eighteen form over half of the Syrian refugee population in Jordan. This led to big demands on educational capability (REACH, 2015). The government has opened 98 additional double-shifted schools to ease burdens on classroom size. Thus, the share of students joining double-shifted schools increased from 7.6% in 2009 to 13.4% in 2014 (Achilli, 2015). This has considerably decreased the Ministry of Education's ambition to reduce the number of double-shifted schools across the country. In the capital Amman and Irbid, nearly half of schools suffer from overloading and have partial capacity to take more students.

Out of 656,400 Syrian refugees in Jordan, some 236,304 are school-aged children (117,306 boys; 118,998 girls). By the end of the 2015/2016 school year, 145,458 Syrian refugee children were enrolled in public schools in camps and host communities, an increase of 16,104 students (12%) compared to the previous academic year (UNESCO, 2017).

The pressure on educational capacity has increased host-community tensions. An assessment by REACH, a joint initiative by two nongovernmental organizations and the United Nations Operational Satellite Applications Program, found 55% of Syrian and Jordanian respondents reported challenges to education as "'very' or 'extremely' urgent (British Embassy, 2014). Furthermore, the survey found 61% of Jordanians reported access to education caused community tensions.

3. Healthcare:

Health care is a must and urgent need for refugees. The refugee influx put the Jordanian health care system under pressure in terms of both finances and service capacity. According to the Ministry of Health, the number of Syrian outpatient visits to primary care centers increased from 68 in January 2012 to 15,975 in March 2013. The number of Syrian

refugee admissions to government hospitals also increased from 300 to 10,330 over that period. As a result of capacity burdens, Jordanians have been increasingly directed to private centers and hospitals to receive care (JRPSC, 2013). Thus, for some citizens, the influx of Syrian refugees has affected the healthcare to be less accessible and more expensive.

Jordan has also witnessed the reemergence of previously eradicated communicable diseases such as tuberculosis, polio, and measles. The provision of vaccinations to Syrians has simultaneously been one of the most important public health missions in Jordan and one of the costliest services provided to Syrian refugees (World Bank, 2015).

Community tensions are rising in response to pressures on the healthcare system. In another REACH survey, 64% of Jordanians and 56% of Syrians reported that access to health care contributed to tensions in their communities (REACH, 2015).

Stress on the healthcare system in Jordan has led to restrictions on services available to Syrian refugees. When the Syrians began arriving in Jordan, the government guaranteed free access to primary and secondary healthcare centers for registered Syrians living in host communities. However, in November 2014, the government repealed free medical services for Syrian refugees, citing an overburdened health sector and budget.

4. Shelter:

The Jordanian housing market had been affected in depth because it is estimated that over 80% of Syrians living outside of refugee camps (MOP, 2014). The Syrian refugee crisis caused Jordan amid a shortage of low-income housing. The growing demand for housing encouraged by Syrians drove up rental prices in the northern Jordanian cities and towns where average rental prices nearly tripled (Mercy Corps, 2013). Stress on the housing sector moved away from both poor Jordanians and Syrians from the housing market.

The Jordanians see the competition to provide shelter is a main cause of tension. The growth in rent caused some social problems for Jordanian communities; reports showed that the overloaded housing costs made young people postpone marriages, as they cannot pay for new housing (Hamai, 2013).

5. Water:

The Syrian refugee presence increased water demand. Jordanian citizens became cautious to save more water fearing that the authorities will pump unused water resources to Syrian refugees. Therefore, competition over water between Jordanians and Syrians caused a threat to Jordan's water supplies (De Châtel, 2014).

The water crisis in Jordan is a severe problem. It is deepened to worse by the Syrians' presence in addition to the historical regional political factors of competition over water. Jordan needs essential developments in the water sector. The Syrian refugee crisis has led attention to the water crisis in Jordan and caused to put it as one of the highest priorities to provide a solution (Francis, 2015). Still, the refugee problem the possibility to push for the causing circumstances that incentivize the conversion of the Jordanian water sector and redirecting them toward greater awareness and practices to this important issue.

6. Security:

Jordan fears of the terrorists among the Syrian refugee influx hiding among the refugees. The terrorists flow is a big challenge to the Jordanian security agencies. They have a great opportunity to stay away from the eyes of security agencies. This situation forces Jordan to take some important procedures in order to avoid being hit again (Malkawi, 2015).

Jordanian fighters join the terrorist groups has links with individuals of the Syrian refugees. Since the beginning of the Syrian Crisis in 2011, has been estimated that more than 30,000 foreign fighters had joined the terroristic groups, such as al-Qaeda and ISIS, in Iraq and Syria. It is

estimated that three thousand Jordanian fighters joined them. The fighters are bushed by frustrations with governance, unemployment, unequal opportunities and the spread of militant jihad beliefs (Schenker, 2014).

The increasing number of deadly attacks carried out by ISIS members from Jordanian nationality, along with the worrying numbers of Syrian refugees and Jordanians jumping into the laps of the Salafi-jihadi groups existing in Iraq and Syria, have triggered big concern in the kingdom (Harel, 2017).

Terroristic actions have direct and indirect effects on security of Jordan's economy. It is noted that as the government spends much of the security in the country, businesses have become vulnerable to probable terrorist targets, with important implications for the foreign investments or performance of multinational firms. Any probable terrorist incidents if affect sensitive economy elements and business in Jordan, the petrol refinery, for example, would cost great loss and creates chaos among people. Terror incidents also occur in Jordan just like other countries, leading to significant socioeconomic consequences (Aly, A. M. S., 2017).

The Jordanian Strategy to contain the impacts of the Syrian refugee crisis:

The Jordanian Strategy to contain the Syrian Refugee crisis is composed of two main parts. First, the Jordanian Response Plan, which is targeting the Syrian refugees and the vulnerable affected Jordanian communities. Second, the International Assistance to Jordan to implement the response plan needs fund, which depends on the Jordanian budget and the foreign fund assistance.

First: The Jordanian Response Plan JRPSC:

The estimated number of people had fled Syria since 2011 is more than 4 million people. With the Syria crisis entering its seventh year in 2017, Jordan is hosting about 1.266 million Syrians, of which 655,833 are registered as refugees (UNHCR, 2017). The government decided to work on providing them their needs, without risking the Jordanian people, institutions and

systems' development gains and opportunities by assisting the vulnerable Jordanians affected by the Syria crisis and giving priority for the Jordanian people requirement for development the from the allocated budget for that purpose. It will strive to be aligned with national priorities to ensure continuity, ownership, and sustainability. The plan was done in coordination with the national development plans.

Going back to 2013, the Jordanian government took an active part in looking forward to respond to the effects of the Syrian crisis within a flexible framework by formulating the National Resilience Plan (NRP 2014), which is concentrated mainly on host communities. Then, the Jordan Response Platform for the Syria Crisis (JRPSC) was established in September 2014 to coordinate, guide and oversight to the preparation, implementation, and monitoring of the Jordan response Plans, which was the first ever comprehensive humanitarian and resilience-based response to the Syria crisis in Jordan (JRPSC, 2015).

The JRPSC brings together high-level representatives of the government, the donor community, UN agencies and the INGO community under one planning and coordination framework. Its mission is to ensure an effective, nationally-owned and coordinated response to the multi-faceted challenges faced by the country as a result of the Syria crisis. It is chaired by the Minister of Planning and International Cooperation (MOPIC). To ensure coherence in the work of the JRPSC, the following 12 Task Forces were established in education, energy, food security, health, justice, livelihood, local governance & municipal services, shelter, social protection, transport, wash, and environment.

Within a timeframe of three years from January 2016 to December 2018 (JRP Guiding, 2015) the current response plan 2016/2018 aims to:

1. Rapidly upscale critical capacities of the central, regional and local authorities to plan, program, coordinate and implement the development response, in order to manage and mitigate the impact of the crisis in a timely, efficient and effective manner.

2. Foster the resilience of:
 - The service delivery system, at the national and local levels, and mitigate the negative impacts on health, education, water and sanitation, in a cost-effective and sustainable manner.
 - Municipal services and infrastructure in areas critically affected by demographic stress, including solid waste management, housing, and energy sectors, thereby advancing more cost effective and sustainable solutions.
3. Meet the immediate needs of:
 - Syrian refugees on and off camps.
 - Vulnerable Jordanians affected by the Syria crisis.
4. Rapidly expand employment and livelihood opportunities, and strengthen the coping mechanism of the most vulnerable groups in the Jordanian population most affected by the crisis.
5. Address social imbalances and strengthen social cohesion in Jordanian communities.
6. Support the Government budget to cope with the additional financial obligations resulting from the Syria Crisis.

1. The Sectorial Response Plan (education, health, shelter, water and security):

A. Response Plan to education sector:

The education component of the JRP aims to ensure sustained access to quality and inclusive education for Syrian refugees and vulnerable Jordanians through the following main pillars (JRPSC, 2015):

1. Increasing access to inclusive education opportunities;
2. Improving the quality of education delivered to all children affected by the crisis; and

3. Strengthening the government capacity to plan and manage the education system in light of the extra pressures on the system

The response to education sector will, therefore, work to boost the capacity of the public education system with much needed extra learning spaces. It will include remedial/catch-up classes for those children who have missed out on weeks or months of schooling and access to improved and diversified certified alternative learning opportunities for children and youth. Capacity building of teachers will also ensure that the quality education is not sacrificed. Moreover, to ensure equal access to all school-aged boys and girls for education, child-centered services in both child-friendly spaces and schools will be provided.

B. Response Plan to health Sector:

The health sector in Jordan continues to face increasing needs and vulnerabilities with continued demand for services from refugees, a changing population demographics, changing epidemiology of disease and increasing rates of determinants of poor health. Rising healthcare costs, of both services and supplies, also raise issues of sustainable financing mechanisms for this increased demand. The health sector response strategy will support durable solutions and aims to maintain humanitarian programming and continue to meet the immediate and short-term health needs of individual refugees whilst also undertaking health systems strengthening and promoting resilience (JRPSC, 2015).

The strategy aims to reinforce the centrality of the national health system to the Syria crisis response. The response spans a range of activities from direct interventions that ensure the short-term critical needs of Jordanians and Syrian refugees are met, through support for primary, secondary, and tertiary health services both in camps, rural and urban settings and systematic investments that reinforce the capacity of the national health system. The response also aims to build the resilience of the public health system through investments in information management and logistics

systems. The health sector response is aligned with the Jordan 2025 National Vision and Strategy, and the National Strategy of Health Sector in Jordan 2015 – 2019.

C. Response Plan to Shelter sector:

In host community urban and rural settings the shelter response plan will continue to focus on the availability, affordability, and quality of shelter and on improving the security of tenure (JRPSC, 2015):

1. Upgrading housing in poor conditions and completing unfinished buildings: not only does this provide adequate, secure shelter for Syrian refugees, but also benefits the Jordanian landlords.
2. Provision of conditional cash for rent: inability to pay rent continues to be one of the major issues, which ties into risk of eviction, protection concerns, and negative coping mechanisms.
3. Distribution of home adaptation kits and developing a winterization strategy for shelters that are not insulated or protected against damp and cold.
4. Lease rights and obligations: dissemination of relevant information messaging.
5. Encouraging resilience and innovation by integrating energy saving, (i.e. solar panels, insulation) and water saving (tap fittings, etc.) components into the shelter response.
6. Better gap analysis and referral mechanisms should be put in place to ensure the needs of more vulnerable households are met. There should be a particular focus on formal links with relevant sectors including Protection and WASH working groups, as a shelter is the main entry point to tackle broader general protection issues.
7. Vulnerability needs assessments will be conducted to assess the needs of men, women, boys, and girls using common criteria as also developed in the Vulnerability Assessment Framework. Men and women will also

be surveyed to understand further their respective uses of the shelter and the degree to which the shelter/modifications address their needs.

D. Response Plan to Water sector:

The vulnerability of the Jordanian population is relatively high, especially for areas categorized as severely vulnerable even in the areas with low concentrations of Syrian refugees. Jordan is also experiencing a natural population growth (of around 2.2 percent annually), nevertheless, two major factors are expanding the gap between water demand and supply: the number of Syrian nationals present in the country and the need to satisfy the demand for the domestic and economic sectors (JRPSC, 2015).

The increase in demand from the Syrian refugees is further reducing the amount and frequency of water available for Jordanians. There is a specific risk associated with the WASH needs of both Syrian refugees and Jordanians living in host communities in terms of cost and efforts⁹¹ and a persistent risk of 'failure to deliver'.

Water scarcity and the state of the water supply and sewage networks in Jordan highlight the magnitude of the investment that Jordan needs as it attempts to meet the additional water and sanitation requirements of the refugees and host communities.

E. Response to Threats in Security sector:

The Jordanian authorities recognized that Jordan is not far away from the dangers that is hidden among some of the Syrian refugees. The increasing sounds of war drums coming from of ISIS toward Jordan stimulated the Kingdom to respond and react in the proper way it sees before it is too late. The Jordanian government adopted a comprehensive security strategy which targets all of the Jordanian society's components including the Syrian refugees. Jordan deployed army troops on the borders with Syria and Iraq with more forces in addition to enforcement of internal policies, laws, regulations, and measures to have more discipline which leads to detaining the terrorist supporters (Schenker, 2014).

Jordan's move to the threats is building the comprehensive strategy to combat security threats depends on five elements which applied fully as well as on the Syrian refugees:

1. Legal modifications in the Anti-Terrorism Law: the parliament of Jordan ratified the legal modifications in the Anti-Terrorism Law in 2014. The government and the security agencies were given wide authorities. New concepts of terrorism issue were added or modified.
2. High ministerial committee for facing terrorism: this committee was formed recently as a result of the increasing Salafist movements in cities and villages of Jordan. The goal of the committee is to face the hardliners politically, socially intellectually and with security means also, if necessary. The representatives of the committee are found all over the Jordanian establishments to observe the extremists closely.
3. The deployment of Jordanian troops across the border with Iraq and Syria. The deployment came after the controlling of ISIS the lands on shared borders of Syria and Iraq with Jordan. During 2016, Jordan kept on strengthening its long border with Iraq and Syria to reduce its proximity danger, specifically, to stop access by terrorists and to control the large influx of refugees.
4. The Jordanian government launched campaigns to promote tolerance thoughts of Islam instead of extremist thoughts. Promoting to follow the peaceful ways of progressive debate and expressing thoughts. The campaigns are fulfilled by the official social society establishments, media, schools, universities and social media space (Altarawneh, 2016).

Second: International Assistance to Jordan:

Jordan is not able to implement the response plan by depending only on its budget. The total needed budget needed fund for the years (2016-2018) is (7,990,882,501) USD to meet the needs of the vulnerable affected

Jordanian communities and the Syrian refugees (MOP, 2015). The budget confirms that Jordan is increasingly dependent on public debt and foreign aid to prop up continued spending. The continuous increasing expenses caused by Syrian refugees' aid had made deficit in the Jordanian budget.

Since the beginning of the crisis in 2011, UN humanitarian appeals were launched to ensure that Syrian refugees receive international assistance and are supported with essential protection services. Jordan cooperates with 71 NGO that works in different humanitarian fields in which they either provide direct fund or implement a various project for the Syrian refugees and the vulnerable affected Jordanian communities (UNHCR, 2017). As of 2015, Jordan has taken the lead in the set-up of the response plan to the impact of the Syria crisis in the country by integrating humanitarian and development responses and resources to address the needs of both Syrian refugees and host communities.

The integration of humanitarian and development aid represents the first time that United Nations development and humanitarian actors have worked so closely together in crisis response (UN, S. Rights, H., & Commission, 2017). The integration of humanitarian and development aid is a suitable response to the difficulties of the Syrian crisis and to the vulnerable affected Jordanian communities. As affected hosting communities come under increased pressure, it is essential that both refugee and Jordanian communities receive support.

Although the international community has indeed helped Jordan, it has however fallen short of the needs and requirements defined in the (JRP2016-18) and all its predecessor plans. This is emblematic of the failure of the orthodox model according to which host countries provide protection space for refugees while the costs are borne by the international community. Yet the international community has no legal obligation to offer financial support (WANA, (2015).

Conclusion:

The Syrian refugee influx into Jordan caused negative impacts as it raised the population by at least 8 percent. The consequences touched almost all aspects of life in Jordan especially the economy, education, healthcare, shelter, water, and security. The highly visible presence of many thousands of refugees living in their midst in urban areas had raised fears over competition for resources and opportunities for the Jordanian people. The Syrian refugee crisis affected the public financial performance. The crisis has placed a significant burden on budgets and is overstretching services across all affected sectors.

Most vulnerable people in Jordan are affected by the presence of Syrian refugees. Wages, prices and housed rent which were already very low became unacceptable to the Jordanians. The Jordanian government concerned about the potentially serious economic effects of the large influx of Syrian refugees to Jordan, including negative effects on the labor market as it caused strong concerns about the effects on available job opportunities, wage levels, working conditions, access to work, etc.

The Jordanian economy sector had been affected by Syrian refugee crisis, especially the most vulnerable Jordanian. The hosting communities have partly benefited from the presence of refugees by providing cheap skillful labor. The business owners have benefited from the increase in consumer demand and the widespread availability of informal Syrian labor. The incomes are threatened by the downward push on informal-sector wages, which were already very low. The Jordanian government gave 200 thousand work permits to the Syrian refugees in the fields of constructions and agriculture, vocational occupations and services, while they are not allowed to work in 19 careers such as administrative positions. Syrians are competing with Jordanians for work opportunities, especially in lower paid jobs, where they seem to possess better experience. At the same time, investment for the Syrian business owners is allowed, but it goes through some legal regulations.

The education sector has been affected significantly by the influx of Syrian refugees. School classrooms are becoming overcrowded, which was already a problem before, with many schools converting to two-shift timings in which Jordanians are taught in the mornings and Syrians in the afternoons resulting in teachers working overtime that they are not compensated for schools are becoming too old and need maintenance or expansion due to population increase. Vulnerability to crowding in classes was found to be more severe in seven districts in governorates with high concentrations of Syrian refugees Thus, education is a number one government service priority.

The rise in the population has affected public services for all. The quality and availability of healthcare have declined as overburdened facilities have struggled to cope with the significant increase in numbers of students and patients. People wait a very long time before receiving medical attention.

Jordanian residents in urban areas have gained from the presence of refugees. Increased housing demand has allowed property owners to set higher rents. The lower-income Jordanian families are being displaced by higher rents.

As for water, the local water shortages have increased as approximately the majority of the Syrian refugees are not living in refugee camps, but in cities and towns. Those hosting communities are severely hit by refugees in the water supply and the portion of water has declined to the Jordanians. The intensive competitions and demands of water force these communities to buy water with high prices to meet their daily needs.

As for the security impact, the Jordanian government fears of the unknown Syrian refugees who might come from radicalization and terrorism. It is noted that some instances in which a number of refugees had participated in violent actions in Jordan and have factional relations in a number of radical and terroristic organizations. They represent a threat to the Jordanian society and to authorities. Jordan recognizes the risk that

some Syrian refugees pose to their security, their economies, their society, and even their culture.

The Jordanian government launched continues comprehensive response plans to contain the impacts of the Syrian refugee crisis. The plans started by 2013/2015, 2014/2016, 2016/2018 continuing to 2017/2019 plan in facing the negative consequences and looking forward to take the advantages of the positive impacts of the Syrian refugees for the benefit of both the refugees and the vulnerable affected hosting community.

The implementing of the JRPSC 2016/2018 had started in January 2016 and to be over by the end of December 2018 for providing protection and emergency humanitarian response to Syrian refugees and to strengthen the resilience of the affected Jordanian people, communities and institutions while at the same time (i) mitigating the ongoing impact of the crisis; (ii) sustaining Jordan's social and economic stability, and (iii) preserving the critical development gains achieved in the last decades.

The JRPSC will include both short-term humanitarian and short and medium term resilience interventions needed to mitigate the impact of the Syrian crisis on Syrian refugees and Jordanian population, including host communities and institutions, chiefly through the provision of humanitarian aid and the strengthening of basic services and Government financing. It will help to ensure that emergency, short, medium and longer-term interventions by Government, the UN, NGOs and private sector are integrated, sequenced and joined up.

Finally, the researcher recommends conducting wider studies on the Syrian refugee crisis in Jordan and its impacts on the Jordanian society.

References:

- Abisaab, J., Balsari, S., Siam, Z. A., Fuller, A., Hamill, K., & Leaning, J. (2014). Syrian Refugees in Jordan: Urgent Issues and Recommendations. FXB Policy Brief, (November), pp:1–9.
- Achilli, L. (2015). Syrian Refugees in Jordan: a Reality Check. Migration Policy Centre EUI, 2 (February), pp:1–12
- Ådnegard, E. (2014). Jordan: Surprisingly Stable. Faculty of Humanities. UNIVERSITY OF OSLO. Norway.
- Ahid, M., & Augustine, A. (2012). The Impact of Global Financial Crisis on Jordan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(16), 108–122.
- Altarawneh, M. (2016, June). [www.alghad..](http://www.alghad.com/articles/953512--مسؤولون-الخطة-الوطنية-لمكافحة-مسؤولون-الخطة-الوطنية-لمكافحة) Retrieved from <http://www.alghad.com/articles/953512--مسؤولون-الخطة-الوطنية-لمكافحة-مسؤولون-الخطة-الوطنية-لمكافحة> Access October 19, 2017.
- Aly, A. M. S., & F. (2017). Saving The Middle East. Middle East Brief. Crown Center for Middle East Studies. Pp: 18-
- Bank, W. (2014). Economic Modelling Using Computational Intelligence. P. 4
- Bank, W. (2015). jordan-economic-monitor-spring-2015. Retrieved from <http://www.worldbank.org/en/country/jordan/publication/jordan-economic-monitor-spring-2015> Access October 25, 2017.
- British Embassy, A. (2014). Education and tensions in Jordanian communities hosting Syrian refugees, 1–16. Retrieved from http://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/REACH_JOR_Report_EducationandTensionsinCommunitiesHostingSyrianRefugees.pdf. Access October 5, 2017.
- De Châtel, F. (2014). The Role of Drought and Climate Change in the Syrian Uprising: Untangling the Triggers of the Revolution. *Middle Eastern Studies*, pp: 521–535.
- Dooley, J. (2009). The Financial Crisis: Impact on the Middle East. pp: 28-31.

- Francis, A. (2015). Jordan's refugee crisis, Carnegie Endowment for International. pp: 1-46.
- Hamai, L., McCormack, R., Niederberger, E., & Lasap, L. (2013). Integrated Assessment of Syrian Refugees in Host Communities. Emergency Food Security and Livelihoods; Water, Sanitation and Hygiene; Protection, (March), p. 8
- Harel, Z. (2017). Hundreds Of Thousands Of Young Jordanians Support ISIS. pp: 1-7.
- Hillesund, S. E. S. and S. (2015). Impact of Syrian refugees on the Jordanian labour market. Research working paper. ILO. pp: 17-19
- JRP Guiding. (2015). Jordan Response Plan 2016-2018 Guiding Framework. pp: 2-3
- JRPSC. (2013). The Jordan Response Platform for the Syria Crisis. Retrieved from <http://www.jrpssc.org/the-jrpssc/> Access September 30, 2017.
- JRPSC. (2015). Jordan Response Plan for Syria Crisis 2016-2018 . pp: 41-136
- Karasapan, O. (2015). Jordan's Syria Refugees," Brookings Institution. pp: 1-3
- Kattaa, M. (2013). Social protection and employment for Syrian refugees in Jordan, 1–26.
- Malkawi, S. (2015). [www.24.ae](http://www.24.ae/article/205558/نددرلأا-للوخذ-رارمتساب-نولولاد-نويشعاد-نويروس-نوضراعم). Retrieved from <http://www.24.ae/article/205558/نددرلأا-للوخذ-رارمتساب-نولولاد-نويشعاد-نويروس-نوضراعم> .aspx Access 5 October 2017.
- Mercy Corps. (2013). Mapping of Host Community-Refugee Tensions in Mafraq and Ramtha, Jordan. pp: 1-3.
- MOP, (2015). National resilience plan 2014 - 2016. Jordanian Government. P. 3
- Nouredine, E., Kuzmova, Y., Akram, S. M., Lang, A., Bidinger, S., & Hites, D. (2015). Protecting Syrian Refugees: Laws, Policies, and Global Responsibility Sharing. Middle East Law and Governance, 7(3), 287–318.

pp: 1-134.

- REACH. (2015). Access To Education for Syrian Refugee Children and Youth in Jordan Host Communities Joint Education Needs Assessment Report Education Sector Working Group. P: 62.
- Remnick, D. (2013). city-of-the-lost @ www.newyorker.com, 3. Retrieved from <https://www.newyorker.com/magazine/2013/08/26/city-of-the-lost>. Access 2 October 2017.
- Ryan, C. R. (2014). Jordanian foreign policy and the Arab spring. Middle East Policy. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mepo.12064> pp: 43-62
- Satik, N. (2013). The Syrian Crisis: An Analysis of Neighboring Countries' Stances, pp: 1-24
- Schenker, D. (2014). Countering the ISIS Threat to Jordan. The Washington Institute. p. 1-2
- Schenker, D. (2014). Jordan Not Out of the Woods Yet. The Washington Institute. p. 2
- UNCHR Report. (2012). Syrians in Jordan. UN. pp: 1-7
- UNESCO. (2017) THE REGIONAL CONFERENCE ON HIGHER EDUCATION IN CRISIS SITUATIONS: "Higher Education in Crisis Situations: Synergizing Policies and Promising Practices to enhance Access, Equity and Quality in the Arab Region," (March), pp: 28–29.
- UN, S. Rights, H., & Commission. (2017). Year: HUMANITARIAN IMPLEMENTATION PLAN (HIP) SYRIA REGIONAL CRISIS. UN. 1-18
- WANA. (2015). forging-new-strategies-protracted-refugee-crises-syrian-refugees-and-host-state-economy. Retrieved from <http://wanainstitute.org/en/publication/forging-new-strategies-protracted-refugee-crises-syrian-refugees-and-host-state-economy>. Access 22 September 2017.
- Weston, P. (2015, August 5). What-is-life-like-inside-the-largest-Syrian-refugee-camp-Zaatari-in-Jordan. Retrieved from <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/middleeast/jordan/11782770/What-is-life-like-inside-the-largest-Syrian-refugee-camp-Zaatari-in-Jordan.html> . Access December 2017.